

Research

Influence of Trust and social presence in m-commerce adoption intention in Bangladesh: An empirical study

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Abstract: *M-commerce is advanced form of traditional business. Although, the initiatives by the companies frequently upgrade their facilities to develop m-commerce, yet consumers' adoption rates are still low in many developing countries. This study aims to investigate the factors that predict consumers' intention to adopt and the influence of consumers' trust and social presence in m-commerce. Further examine moderating role of social presence with social influence and trust in m-commerce adoption intention. A theoretical model is integrating with the help of Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology model (UTAUT2), trust and social presence. The quantitative data is collected (n = 418) and analyzed through Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The research result shows that performance expectancy, social influence, trust and social presence significantly influence the adoption intention. Social presence has interacting moderator effect on social influence, and trust. However, effort expectancy has not significantly influence on adoption in m-commerce. The findings have some theoretical enlightenment and practical implications.*

Keywords: *M-commerce; adoption intention; trust; social presence; UTAUT2*

1. Introduction

Rapid development of Web2.0 technologies significantly influences the consumers' preferences across the globe. For example, mobile commerce (m-commerce) offers an opportunity for consumers to access merchants, share personal opinions and make more precise shopping decisions [1, 2], which develops more sociable and trustworthy in online business. M-commerce is viewed as a subset of e-commerce [3], allowing people buying and selling products anywhere any time. Research reported that in 2011 m-commerce transactions were valued at \$105.9 billion

and reached \$617 billion by 2016 [4]. Moreover, in developing countries entrepreneurs are doing better business through m-commerce; 70% of order were confirmed through m-commerce [5, 6]. These indicate that both buyer and sellers have a good opportunity of m-commerce in developing countries.

Through technological models sellers could understand how consumers utilize and adopt m-commerce to develop more efficient and effective interfaces and formulate their strategies. Previous research on m-commerce through technology acceptance model confirms intention and perceptions related to predictive m-commerce purchase intentions. In several studies we found that trust is a reliable predictor in m-commerce purchase intentions [7, 8]. Other scholars indicated that performance expectancy and effort expectancy predict m-commerce adoption [8, 9]. Consumers adopt m-commerce based on the views of others that indicates social influence also affects m-commerce purchase intentions [10, 11]. Recent studies on m-commerce investigate the relationship between consumers' perceptions and intention in m-commerce; but very few studies included performance and effort expectancies, social influence, the facilitating conditions of m-commerce trust and perceived risk, and customer purchase intentions [7, 12]. Moreover studies conducted on m-commerce adoption intention with UTAUT2 are very few; especially social presence with UTAUT2 is quite a few. According to Budzanowska-Drzewiecka [13] maintained the fundamental behavioral dynamics associated with m-commerce requires further research. Scholarly evidence suggests that performance and effort expectancies, social influence, and trust may be significant factors in m-commerce purchase or adoption intentions [12], which may be applied in business to develop competitive advantages. However, it is unclear which of those components will enhance consumers' adoption intention.

In order to support more accurate prediction of adoption intention of m-commerce in the developing countries, should adding important determinants as “social presence”. In addition, UTAUT2 is widely used in developed countries, but very few studies in developing countries. Therefore, the decision to adopt UTAUT2, as well as using PLS-SEM for analysis will definitely contribute to the existing literatures by variation of research design and methodology. Considering the above-mentioned points, this study aims to examine the determinants of UTAUT2 and trust with social presence to find consumers' adoption intention and how does social presence moderates the relationship between UTAUT2 determinant and trust in the context of m-commerce. Based on the UTAUT2 [14], we construct a theoretical research model

to identify the adoption intentions in m-commerce. First aim of this paper will examine the combined influences of UTAUT2, trust, social presence and intention on consumer's m-commerce adoption intentions. Second, aim is to identify consumers' social presence moderating effect in between of social influence and trust through PLS-SEM (Partial least squared-Structural equation modeling).

The remaining paper is organized as follows. First, we summarize a theoretical framework. Second, we recommend the study model and hypotheses. Third, we deal with the methodology. Fourth, we conduct an empirical study. To conclude, we discuss the limitation and possible future research.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. M-commerce

The concept of m-commerce is well-established in the marketing literature [15]. M-commerce encourages the vitality of e-commerce platforms through social networks, and improves the business prosperity by connecting consumers with merchants and consumers with each other [16]. M-commerce involved and builds on three key traits of e-commerce: technologies based media, social connections and business activities [17]. Considering above literature advantage of m-commerce, traders are now able to advertise their products in their pages; upload videos and pictures on e-commerce webs and communicate with consumers in several ways. On the other hand consumers can respond to products on different platforms and communicate with others. Many companies are competing with each other for better sales and reputation in m-commerce. Thus m-commerce supports Twitter, Facebook, and provides numerous channels of B2C and C2C links for both consumers and merchants. The in-depth study of m-commerce can assist us to better understand m-commerce and guide academic or practical research.

2.2. The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology model

Technology has become an integral part of our daily life and makes our life easy. Technology with mobile phones and devices support us to purchase and sells. There are few studies that identify the factors that affect customer's intention to use m-commerce in Bangladesh. Therefore, need for studies on how operators apply and adopt new technology. Prior studies [4] have used several theories to examine the factors affecting technology intention; as example,

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Diffusion of innovation theory (DOI). This study utilizes the concept of UTAUT2 to explain consumer m-commerce adoption intentions by integrating consumers' trust in online sellers and social presence. Numerous studies [18, 19] discussed the influence of performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influence on the intention to use a technology and the actual use of that technology [19, 20]. The construct “Trust” incorporated with the UTAUT, been considered as another predictor of the use of a technology. Authors utilized “Trust” as a construct in different ways as comparable to “prior behavior” or “prior use” which individuals believe that their behavior is automatic [21].

2.3. Social presence (SP)

Social presence is defined as the experience of observing others' existences in the medium and interactions. Social presence plays a significant role in m-commerce shopping environment, which lacks a face-to-face interaction between consumers and merchants [22]. Social presence explains the medium to communicate and to convey social signals, such as virtual agents [23], socially-rich message [24], human-like interface [25], 3D displays [26], telepresence [27].

3. Research model and Hypotheses:

Drawing upon the theoretical background this study identifies six constructs of the research model: Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, Social Influence, and Trust with direct and moderating effect of Social Presence, and m-commerce adoption intention. Five hypotheses examine the effects on consumer's' m-commerce adoption intention and hypothesis examines impact on adoption intention. The last two hypotheses test the moderating role of social presence on the relationship between social Influence and trust with consumers' adoption intention in m-commerce. Based on the following assumptions, a study model has been developed (Fig. 1 shows the model of this study).

Fig.1. Proposed Study model

3.1. Performance Expectancy

One of the important factors of UTAUT2 is Performance Expectancy which has been originated from perceived usefulness, the relative advantage, job-fit, extrinsic motivates [14]. Performance Expectancy is defined as the strength of an individuals' belief that m-commerce will help to better perform a task [28]. Numerous studies on the technology intention, perceived usefulness of a technology such as mobile credit, was found to have a positive effect on behavioral intentions to use mobile credit [29]. Besides, Performance Expectancy was established to have considerable effect on the consumers' adopts of m-commerce [18, 30], mobile payment system [31, 32], mobile internet [28, 33]. Hence, it is believed that Performance Expectancy will impact users' to adopt m-commerce. Therefore, the ensuing hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Performance Expectancy significantly influence consumers' m-commerce adopt intention.

3.2. Effort expectancy

Effort Expectancy has been developed as part of the theory of UTAUT2 from past studies constructs like 'perceived ease of use' 'complexity' and 'ease of use'. EE mentions the degree of security linked with consumers' use of technology. Earlier studies supports that EE was significant in determining a person's desire to adopt a new technology by Venkatesh et al.[28]. M-commerce one of the technology represents consumers with numerous opportunities such as not being limited to specific products with particular locations. Past studies used this constructs to identify behavioral intention to adopt m-commerce in different countries [28, 31, 32, 34].Therefore we rationally developed another hypothesis as:

H2: Effort expectancy significantly influence consumers' m-commerce adopt intention.

3.3. Social influence

Social influence is conceived of as a composite of factors, including components such as social image, informal influence, maintenance, and critical mass [19]. Social influence indicates to the consumers' accepting information from peers as evidence about authenticity and forming an judgment on that basis [35]. Critical mass mentions that when a technology reaches a significant market penetration and its' perceived value is increasing in society, in that way enticing more users and accelerating adoption. Social influence can also maintain an individual's social image, improving that individual's position and performance in a society. Social influence figures prominently in studies pertaining to technology use behavior [15, 18]; with the finding that adoption of new technologies is predicted by social norms and influences. As m-commerce is a relatively new technology, social influence is likely to be an important predictor of its adoption.

H3: Social influence significantly influences consumers' m-commerce adopt intention.

3.4. Trust

Trust is considered as an important construct in developing consumers' m-commerce adoption intention. Moorman et al. [36] define trust as, "partners are willingness to relay on an exchange and has confidence". Numerous studies have shown that if trust is present then there is a greater willingness to buy from an online seller [4, 37, 38] and better user acceptance of electronic services [39]. Previous research found that online shoppers' consumer trust is important to online commerce. Therefore, trust has been regarded as a key driver for online adoption [15]. Trust becomes crucial under some circumstances like transactional relationship between a buyer and seller, especially in situations such as an interaction with the unknown e-vendor [40]. Thus, we hypothesis that:

H4. Trust significantly influence consumers' m-commerce adopt intention.

3.5. Social presence

In online business consumers can't touch and measure the quality of real products, they can see the appearance of the products and their descriptions as materials, size, weights, etc. This kind of reality brings consumers the unreal sense of commodity existence and social presence. Few researchers believe that, one of the main reasons to reduce deals for communications among consumers [25]. Because, m-commerce users are eager to spend a lot of time reading online

reviews. They not only reading and getting information, but also for feeling the social experience of experiencing others' consumption. Through social presence with consumers' interactions can decrease the merchants. The reduction of information asymmetry helps to improve consumers' trust in merchants. Thus, we suggest the following hypothesis:

H5. Social presence significantly influence consumers' m-commerce adopt intention.

Social presence is a multi-dimensional concept, which has several elements for various perspectives [22]. In this study, we focus on social presence through social influence and trust which could interacts consumers provided information and support in online platforms. Though, social networking platforms permit consumers to interact with each other. Social presence through social influence can reduce or increase the uncertainty of consumers to merchants. Social presence encourages consumers to get the higher level of information of goods through social presence. For example, users in m-commerce provide a lot of information, such as consumer's experience, product quality, consumers' advice and so on. These notes provided by the m-commerce pages can easily record those information and gain knowledge from it, which can more easily reduce the uncertainty of consumers to adopt. These will positively influence consumers' trust in the adoption intention. Hence, it means that through social influence and social presence consumers to get a higher level of information that could increase consumers' trust through visuals or texts, which finally enhances consumers' adoption intention. Hence, the subsequent hypotheses are formulated as:

H6a. Social presence significantly influences the relationship between social influence and consumers' intentions in m-commerce adopt intention.

H6b. Social presence significantly influences the relationship between trust and consumers' intentions in m-commerce adopt intention.

4. Methods

This section we focus on the empirical analysis. According to existing literature we develop a survey questionnaire. Then we describe the data collection procedure as well as draw demographic characteristics. After that, portraits relevant data analysis techniques for the study.

4.1. Questionnaire design

A structured questionnaire is designed and all scales use the seven-point (i.e. “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (7)) Likert-type response format. In order to keep a degree of rationality, all the constructs are taken from existing studies. Specifically, the items for performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and intention dimensions are adapted from Venkatesh et al. [28]. The items for the consumers’ trust in adoption intention are adapted from Shaw; Sing & Sinha, [38, 41] and social presence are adopted from Jiang, Rashid & Wang [22]. The constructs items and their sources are shown in Table 1.

Table-1: Convergent validity of measurement model.

	Loading	α	AVE	CR
Performance expectancy (PE)		Venkatesh et al. (2012)		
PE1	0.861			
PE2	0.791	0.801	0.615	0.892
PE3	0.799			
PE4	0.753			
Effort expectancy (EE)		Venkatesh et al. (2012))		
EE1	0.801			
EE2	0.754			
EE3	0.721	0.799	0.595	0.856
EE4	0.701			
Social influence (SI)		Venkatesh et al. (2012)		
SI1	0.898			
SI2	0.776	0.815	0.617	0.901
SI3	0.712			
Trust (TR)		Shaw(2014); Singh & Sinha (2020)		
TR1	0.806			
TR2	0.757			
TR3	0.789	0.787	0.612	0.863
TR4	0.786			
Social presence (SP)		Jiang et al. 2019		
SP1	0.840			
SP2	0.839			
SP3	0.891	0.822	0.623	0.843
SP4	0.827			
SP5	0.801			
Intentions (IN)		Venkatesh et al. (2012))		
IN 1	0.867			
IN2	0.798	0.815	0.617	0.901
IN 3	0.761			
IN 4	0.723			

4.2. Sample population and data collection

We do some preliminary work before starting the main study. First, we unify a group of people which contains six Master's and Ph.D. students with specialized skills in survey design. Second,

by the group's suggestions critical and minor changes have done with regarding to the sequence and word. Third, to receive feedbacks we initially sent out 15 questionnaires. After analyzing these questionnaires, we confirm the final version of the questionnaire. The data is collected through self-administered questionnaires from main different cities of Bangladesh, e.g., Dhaka, Chumillah, Chylet, Chittagong, Rajsahi, Bogra, Khulna, Barisal, Rangpur, etc. The survey is managed with the help of people who have the experience of data collection. The main target population includes those who are close to shopping malls and universities. Respondents are first asked if they have shopping experiences on social commerce pages through Facebook, messenger, whatsapp, IMO, or mobile. We invite those people who are experienced and request to participate in the survey questionnaire. Our target respondents' age groups are between 18 to 45 years old; because these groups of people are early adopters of any product or technology. With the help of researchers, respondents will get a gift after completing the survey. A total of 474 questionnaires are collected and 56 of these are rejected because of missing data; and hence, 418 questionnaires are used for the final study analysis. The details of demographics are shown in Table 2.

Table-2: Descriptive statistics of respondents' characteristics.

Measures	Items	Frequency	(%)
Gender	Male	228	54.5%
	Female	190	45.5%
Age	16-25	129	30.9%
	26-35	197	47.1%
	36-45 ⁺	92	22.0%
Education	High School	39	9.3%
	College	69	16.5%
	Bachelors	171	40.9%
	Masters	139	33.3%
M-commerce purchase frequency	Several times a week	52	12.4%
	Several times a month	278	66.5%
	Once a week	49	11.7%
	Once a month	39	9.4%

4.3. Evaluation method

We use the structural equation modeling (SEM) approach through a partial least squares (PLS) method to evaluate the structural model. According to Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, and Mena [42] PLS is a second generation technique, which is used to simultaneously test the measurement and

structural model and also combines the regression and component factor analysis (CFA). In this study, we use the Smart-PLS 3.2.8 software to conduct a PLS estimation.

5. Analysis results

5.1. Common method bias

For the social researcher Common method bias is the concerning issue. Hence we calculate common method bias with the help of the variance inflation factor (VIF) [43]. In the PLS-SEM the results of VIT should be less than or equal 3.3; and in our study the value of VIF is between 1.86 and 2.39. Therefore, in our study there is no serious issue of common method bias.

5.2. Measurement model

To check the reliability and validity of constructs used in this study, we perform internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminate validity [44]. We assess above validities by analyzing Cronbach's alpha (α), factor loadings, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE). To find the reasonable convergent validity we take the all factor loadings are above minimum level 0.7. The minimum value for α is 0.7, which shows that the data has an internal consistency [42]. The value of CR of all constructs is above 0.8 and the value of AVE of all constructs is above 0.5. Hence, the results show a reasonable convergent validity (Table 1). The discriminant validity confirms whether the construct measures are different from other constructs or not [22, 44]. The square root of the AVE is above than the correlation between variables, which shows the reasonable discriminant validity (table-3).

Table-3: Measurement model and discriminant validity.

	PE	EE	SI	TR	SS	IN
Performance Expectancy (PE)	0.841					
Effort Expectancy (EE)	0.496	0.837				
Social Influence (SI)	0.389	0.436	0.791			
Trust (TR)	0.467	0.571	0.432	0.856		
Social support (SS)	0.368	0.423	0.501	0.513	0.803	
Intention (IN)	0.321	0.347	0.378	0.443	0.513	0.829

5.3. Structural model

The results of the study model shows in Fig. 2. We test the estimated path of coefficients of the structural model and assess our hypotheses. Performance Expectancy has a positive effect between consumers adoption intention in m-commerce, supporting H1 ($\beta=0.365$, $p < 0.001$).

Effort Expectancy has a positive effect, but not strong enough to support the hypothesis between consumers adoption intention in m-commerce, supporting H2 ($\beta=0.041$, $p < 0.067$); i.e. we can reject the hypothesis. Still, social Influence has a positive effect on consumers' adoption intention in m-commerce, supporting H3 ($\beta=0.291$, $p < 0.01$). In addition, consumers' trust in m-commerce has a positive effect on their adoption intentions, supporting H4 ($\beta=0.351$, $p < 0.001$). Finally, social presence also has a positive effect on consumers' adoption intention in m-commerce, supporting H5 ($\beta=0.178$, $p < 0.009$). According to Hair et al., [42] the value of R^2 should be above 0.2; because, in behavioral research the value above than 0.2 is considered as highly relative and acceptable. In this study, the $R^2 = 0.635$ for consumers trust on m-commerce adoption intentions.

Fig. 2. Results of the model tests

Next, social presence's moderating effect is evaluated. When the moderating effect is entered into the model, the R^2 rises to 0.695, and R^2 has a change of 6.0%. The result shows that Social presence support's (H5a: $\beta=0.139$, $p < 0.029$) moderating effect on the relationship between social influence and consumers' intention in m-commerce adoption intention. Furthermore, Social presence moderating effect on the relationship between trust and consumers' intention in m-commerce adoption intention is significant (H5b: $\beta=0.156$, $p < 0.035$). Hence, H5a, and H5b are supported (see Table 4).

Table 4: Structural model results (hypothesis testing).

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	Std. error	t-value	Decision	R ²
H1	PE→ IN	0.365	0.065	7.695***	Supported	0.635
H2	EE→ IN	0.041	0.032	1.531 ^{ns}	Not Supported	
H3	SI→ IN	0.291	0.045	3.96**	Supported	
H4	TR→ IN	0.351	0.061	6.775***	Supported	
H5	SP→ IN	0.178	0.039	3.902**	Supported	
H6b	SI*SP→ IN	0.139	0.049	2.001*	Supported	0.695
H6a	TR*SP→ IN	0.156	0.053	2.214**	Supported	

6. Discussion and implications

6.1. Discussion

After the above empirical analysis, our study model incorporates the UTAUT2 theory with trust and social presence which are proved to be effective. Several findings can be derived from this study. First, this article expresses the validity of two elements of UTAUT2 named performance expectancy and Social influence. In this study, the factor effort expectancy has no significant effect on m-commerce user adoption. The result that effect expectancy did not reflect the probability of consumer's adoption intention, not only appeared in this study, but also in a few of previous studies [45]. It may be for the reason of different country and culture [46]. Furthermore, performance expectancy and social influence had a significant influence on adoption intention. Venkatesh et al. found that social influence has important effects in the use of the technology [28]. UTAUT2 through consumers' interactions is found to be a positively effect on consumers' trust in m-commerce adoption intention [22]. Consumers frequently reaction of feelings, reviews, recommendations and facts about after-sale services of others before shopping through m-commerce. These reduce the uncertainty of consumers to merchants through m-commerce. The reduction of bad reviews or information asymmetry helps to improve consumers' trust in m-commerce adoption.

Furthermore, social presence is identified as one of the factors with the greatest predictive value for user adoption. Friedkin and Johnsen point out in their research, a person was difficult to maintain one's own opinion on an issue when the other members of his group had relatively uniform opinions on the issue [47]. Moreover, the results show that social presence between consumers significantly affects the consumers' trust in m-commerce. So, we conclude that social

presence consumers play an important role to express a sense of social influence, which consequently raises consumers' trust in m-commerce adoption. The statistical results of the structural model confirm the positive effect of social presence in m-commerce adoption. That is in line with earlier studies [34, 48]. Lastly, the PLS-SEM results show that social presence is positively moderating the relationship between social influence and consumers' trust in m-commerce adoption. That means, social support is also positively moderating effect in the relationship between UTAUT2 and consumers' trust in m-commerce adoption.

6.2. Theoretical implications

The research outcomes have the following theoretical implication. First, this study draws our attention to the necessity of considering the role of social presence, trust and determinants of UTAUT2 in m-commerce adoption. Second, we find that social presence moderates the relationship between social influence and trust. Social presence can help us better understand the different UTAUT2 determinants and trust effects on intention. Moreover, trust and social presence plays an important role in m-commerce adaptation.

6.3. Practical implications

Based on the above research conclusions and enlightenment, this study also has some practical implications. First, this study clearly tells merchants which determinants of UTAUT2 will develop consumers' adoption intention and how does trust improve adoption intention. Using these merchants can improve the level of interactions to develop consumers' trust and hence can improve adoption intention. For example, merchants can bring the sociability to customers through social influence. Second, this study draws merchants' attention to the necessity role of social presence, and consumers' trust to improve consumers' shopping intentions in m-commerce. The results suggest that a higher level of social presence is essential between social influence and consumers' trust to improve business in m-commerce. For example, the guiding information of shopping is added to help the use of new technologies which will increase consumer adoption intention. Third, the application of technology is not only improves shopping efficiency, but also brings unique psychological experience for consumers to adopt. We suggest that businesses consider the potential role of technology and considering the application of new technologies. Like the social presence that brings to consumers, technology can weaken the virtuality of the

network and improves consumers' trust. This concept will help businesses to think the potential long term benefits of technology investment.

6.4. Limitations and future work

Like all other studies, this study also has some limitations. First, data was collected from major cities; hence future research needs to use the data from all districts. Second, the variables used in this study have been measured at a single point of time. Future studies may consider the longitudinal technique to confirm the results. Third, the target population for this study was the people 16 to 45 years of age. Future studies can target people with other age groups to get ample knowledge of consumers' m-commerce adoption intention. Finally, this study is limited to adoption intention. Future study may examine the actual behavior and consider other constructs that may explain differences between intention and behavior.

References

1. Ström, R., M. Vendel, and J. Bredican, *Mobile marketing: A literature review on its value for consumers and retailers*. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 2014. **21**(6): p. 1001-1012.
2. Mahapatra, S., *Mobile shopping among young consumers: an empirical study in an emerging market*. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management, 2017. **45**(9): p. 930-949.
3. Zhang, J. and Y. Yuan, *M-commerce versus internet-based E-commerce: the key differences*. AMCIS 2002 Proceedings, 2002: p. 261.
4. Rahman, M.M. and T. Sloan, *User adoption of mobile commerce in Bangladesh: Integrating perceived risk, perceived cost and personal awareness with TAM*. The International Technology Management Review, 2017. **6**(3): p. 103-124.
5. Islam, M.S., et al., *Intention to adopt mobile banking in Bangladesh: an empirical study of emerging economy*. International Journal of Business Information Systems, 2019. **31**(1): p. 136-151.
6. Kader, R., *Future Startup*. Inside Ajkerdeal's Big Plan To Take e-Commerce Beyond Dhaka Retrieved from <http://futurestartup.com/2016/12/19/inside-ajkderdeals-big-plan-take-e-commerce-beyond-dhaka>, 2016.
7. Chunxiang, L., *Study on mobile commerce customer based on value adoption*. Journal of Applied Sciences, 2014. **14**(9): p. 901-909.
8. Nassuora, A.B., *Understanding factors affecting the adoption of m-commerce by consumers*. Journal of Applied Sciences, 2013. **13**(6): p. 913-918.
9. Wang, M., et al. *Understanding Perceived Platform Trust and Institutional Risk in Peer-to-Peer Lending Platforms from Cognition-Based and Affect-Based Perspectives*. in PACIS. 2014.

10. Pelet, J.-É. and P. Papadopoulou, *The effect of colors of e-commerce websites on consumer mood, memorization and buying intention*. European Journal of Information Systems, 2012. **21**(4): p. 438-467.
11. Zhou, T. and Y. Lu, *Examining mobile instant messaging user loyalty from the perspectives of network externalities and flow experience*. Computers in Human Behavior, 2011. **27**(2): p. 883-889.
12. Zhang, L., J. Zhu, and Q. Liu, *A meta-analysis of mobile commerce adoption and the moderating effect of culture*. Computers in human behavior, 2012. **28**(5): p. 1902-1911.
13. Budzanowska-Drzewiecka, M., *Individual determinants of propensity to make purchases as part of e-commerce and m-commerce in Polish young consumers*. Jagiellonian Journal of Management, 2015. **1**(1): p. 7-21.
14. Venkatesh, V., et al., *User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view*. MIS quarterly, 2003: p. 425-478.
15. Chou, Y.-H.D., T.-Y.D. Li, and C.-T.B. Ho, *Factors influencing the adoption of mobile commerce in Taiwan*. International Journal of Mobile Communications, 2018. **16**(2): p. 117-134.
16. Narakorn, P. and T. Seesupan, *Social Commerce Constructs and Buyer-Seller Relationship Quality as a predictor of Intention to Co-Creation in Branding*. Modern Applied Science, 2019. **13**(2).
17. Huang, Z. and M. Benyoucef, *From e-commerce to social commerce: A close look at design features*. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications, 2013. **12**(4): p. 246-259.
18. Blaise, R., M. Halloran, and M. Muchnick, *Mobile Commerce Competitive Advantage: A Quantitative Study of Variables that Predict M-Commerce Purchase Intentions*. Journal of Internet Commerce, 2016(1): p. 1-19.
19. Blaise, R., M. Halloran, and M. Muchnick, *Mobile commerce competitive advantage: A quantitative study of variables that predict m-commerce purchase intentions*. Journal of Internet Commerce, 2018. **17**(2): p. 96-114.
20. Sim, J.J., et al. *Trust in Vendor and Perceived Effectiveness of E-Commerce Institutional Mechanisms in M-Commerce Adoption: A Revised UTAUT Model*. in *2018 8th IEEE International Conference on Control System, Computing and Engineering (ICCSCE)*. 2018. IEEE.
21. Limayem, M., S.G. Hirt, and C.M.K. Cheung, *How Habit Limits the Predictive Power of Intention: The Case of Information Systems Continuance*. Mis Quarterly. **31**(4): p. 705-737.
22. Jiang, C., R.M. Rashid, and J. Wang, *Investigating the role of social presence dimensions and information support on consumers' trust and shopping intentions*. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 2019. **51**: p. 263-270.
23. Hess, T.J., M. Fuller, and D.E. Campbell, *Designing interfaces with social presence: Using vividness and extraversion to create social recommendation agents*. Journal of the Association for Information Systems, 2009. **10**(12): p. 1.
24. Gefen, D. and D.W. Straub, *Consumer trust in B2C e-Commerce and the importance of social presence: experiments in e-Products and e-Services*. Omega, 2004. **32**(6): p. 407-424.
25. Pavlou, P.A., H. Liang, and Y. Xue, *Understanding and mitigating uncertainty in online exchange relationships: A principal-agent perspective*. MIS quarterly, 2007: p. 105-136.

26. Wang, X., et al., *Exploring embodied social presence of youth with Autism in 3D collaborative virtual learning environment: A case study*. Computers in Human Behavior, 2016. **55**: p. 310-321.
27. Algharabat, R., et al., *The effect of telepresence, social presence and involvement on consumer brand engagement: An empirical study of non-profit organizations*. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 2018. **40**: p. 139-149.
28. Venkatesh, V., J.Y. Thong, and X. Xu, *Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology*. MIS quarterly, 2012. **36**(1): p. 157-178.
29. Tan, G.W.-H., et al., *NFC mobile credit card: The next frontier of mobile payment?* Telematics & Informatics. **31**(2): p. 292-307.
30. Ooi, K.B., J.J. Hew, and B. Lin, *Unfolding the privacy paradox among mobile social commerce users: a multi-mediation approach*. Behaviour & Information Technology, 2018. **37**(2009): p. 1-21.
31. Morosan, C. and A. DeFranco, *It\'s about time: Revisiting UTAUT2 to examine consumers\' intentions to use NFC mobile payments in hotels*. International Journal of Hospitality Management. **53**: p. 17-29.
32. Slade, E.L., M.D. Williams, and Y.K. Dwivedi, *Devising a research model to examine adoption of mobile payments: An extension of UTAUT2*. Marketing Review. **14**(3): p. 310-335.
33. Zendehdel, M. and L. Paim, *Predicting Intention of Mobile Internet Usage in Malaysia: Extending the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology*. 2016.
34. Hajli, N., et al., *A social commerce investigation of the role of trust in a social networking site on purchase intentions*. Journal of Business Research, 2017. **71**: p. 133-141.
35. Bapna, R. and A. Umyarov, *Do your online friends make you pay? A randomized field experiment on peer influence in online social networks*. Management Science, 2015. **61**(8): p. 1902-1920.
36. Moorman, C., R. Deshpande, and G. Zaltman, *Factors affecting trust in market research relationships*. Journal of marketing, 1993. **57**(1): p. 81-101.
37. Rind, M.M., et al. *Modeling User's Trust in M-Commerce Acceptance: A Conceptual Framework in Context of Pakistan*. in *2015 4th International Conference on Advanced Computer Science Applications and Technologies (ACSAT)*. 2015. IEEE.
38. Singh, N. and N. Sinha, *How perceived trust mediates merchant's intention to use a mobile wallet technology*. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 2020. **52**: p. 101894.
39. Carter, L. and V. Weerakkody, *E-government adoption: A cultural comparison*. Information systems frontiers, 2008. **10**(4): p. 473-482.
40. Zhou, T., *An empirical examination of initial trust in mobile payment*. Wireless personal communications, 2014. **77**(2): p. 1519-1531.
41. Shaw, N., *The mediating influence of trust in the adoption of the mobile wallet*. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 2014. **21**(4): p. 449-459.
42. Hair Jr, J.F., et al., *Advanced issues in partial least squares structural equation modeling*. 2017: Sage Publications.
43. Kock, N., *Common method bias in PLS-SEM: A full collinearity assessment approach*. International Journal of e-Collaboration (IJeC), 2015. **11**(4): p. 1-10.

44. Hair, J.F., C.M. Ringle, and M. Sarstedt, *PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet*. Journal of Marketing theory and Practice, 2011. **19**(2): p. 139-152.
45. Lee, S.W., H.J. Sung, and H.M. Jeon, *Determinants of Continuous Intention on Food Delivery Apps: Extending UTAUT2 with Information Quality*. Sustainability, 2019. **11**(11): p. 3141.
46. Thomas, T., L. Singh, and K. Gaffar, *The utility of the UTAUT model in explaining mobile learning adoption in higher education in Guyana*. International Journal of Education and Development using ICT, 2013. **9**(3).
47. Friedkin, N.E. and E.C. Johnsen, *Social influence and opinions*. Journal of Mathematical Sociology, 1990. **15**(3-4): p. 193-206.
48. Lu, B., W. Fan, and M. Zhou, *Social presence, trust, and social commerce purchase intention: An empirical research*. Computers in Human Behavior, 2016. **56**: p. 225-237.

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